

DISTRIBUTION MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN LOGISTICS

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Abstract:

Learning first mile and last mile operations and people management for planning in the morning loads and how allocating equally the field executives. The mapping is done for the auto dispatch of shipments and shipment will assign to particular FE and arrange accordingly and lead to delivery. After completion of work turn back to office and handover the remaining shipments and available cash of COD shown while were closing in the EOD. First mile assign and they carry the ship from the origin and handover and bagged in the office. Finally lead to the hub by transporting.

Key Words: Distribution, Planning & E-Commerce

Introduction:

A logistics company supporting third party e-commerce sectors and other institutions. It helps in transporting the goods from the origin to the customers place or the delivery place. The first mile agent will pick up the shipments from the origin and they hand over to the concern office and from there the shipments are packed and transported to the nearest respective hubs and the sill sort the shipments and sent to the concern hubs and from the concern local hub they send the particular shipments at concern DC. From the concern delivery hub the assign to FE and make delivery of the product so it is acting as a third party courier Company. They charge for the service in according with the shipment size and if the shipment was in COD. The will bet cashed for that or if it is prepaid they deliver the shipment and get delivery OTP and update the shipment as delivery.

Objectives:

To enrich knowledge about effective transportation from origin to customer

Application of Learning

- Planning
- People management
- Auto route mapping
- FM dispatch
- LM dispatch
- Outbound
- Auditing
- Load clearing
- Team leading

Problems in TDM

- Seasonal Demand Fluctuations
- Distance and infrastructure
- High Fuel Cost
- Traffic Connection
- Environmental Concern
- Inventory Management
- Driver Shortage

Importance of TDM

- Land and Sea Hybrid Transportation
- Rail and Road Hybrid Transportation
- Last-Mile Hybrid Transportation
- Multi Modal; Transportation

Opportunities in TDM

- Distribution Managers
- Warehouse Managers
- Inventory Managers
- Purchasing managers
- Freight Forwarders
- Production Managers
- E-Commerce Logistics Managers

Future Scope of LSCM Manager:

Supply Chain Management, logistics and procurement help businesses stay competitive by helping track and coordinate the cost-effective and efficient movement of goods and services, The profitability of an organization is based on the importance of management of the flow of goods and services between locations and businesses, growth of supply chain management, logistics, and purchasing on par with average rates and above average. Therefore, demand professionals skilled in supply chain management, procurement, and logistics roles aren't likely to dissipate.

General Concept:

Supply Chain Management deals with the management of the flow of goods and services between locations and businesses. Movement and storage of raw materials, work-in-process inventory and finished goods along with end-to-end order fulfillment from the point of origin to the point of consumption. Major supply chain management practices are heavily drawn on industrial engineering, operations management, systems

engineering, logistics, procurement, marketing as well as information technology and strive for an integrated, multi method, multidisciplinary approach. Wide applicability in diverse sectors, supply chain management tremendous career scope. An interest in supply chain management, procurement, and logistics management can opt for general growth.

Conclusion:

The integration of hybrid transportation modes within our coir distribution system marked a significant milestone in our pursuit of efficiency and sustainability. By combining road, sea, and air transport strategically not only optimized delivery timelines but have also reduced output. This innovative approach has allowed reaching global markets with speed and precision, meeting the diverse demands of customers.

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